

THE SPECIFIC EFFECT OF THE DRUG "BAKLASAN" IN CEREBROVASCULAR DISEASES AND ITS PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE TODAY

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Abstract. Swimming rats for 30 minutes led to a decrease in the level of specific binding of GABA by the plasma membranes of the adrenal glands of intact rats, but not in rats that were repeatedly administered hydrocortisone to inhibit the basal activity of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal cortex system and in which the level of amino acid receptor was significantly higher than the control. Pre-stress administration of baclofen and gamma-L-aminobutyryltaurine did not change the specific binding of GABA, despite the effect of the drugs on the concentration of corticosteroids in the blood of animals.

Keywords: GABA, hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal cortex system, gamma-L-aminobutyryltaurine, Baclofen, encephalopathy, amino acids – glutamate, spasm, neurotoxic effect.

СПЕЦИФИЧЕСКОЕ ДЕЙСТВИЕ ПРЕПАРАТА «БАКЛАСАН» ПРИ ЦЕРЕБРОВАСКУЛЯРНЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯХ И ЕГО ПРАКТИЧЕСКОЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ СЕГОДНЯ

Аннотация. Плавание крыс в течение 30 минут приводило к снижению уровня специфического связывания ГАМК плазматическими мембранами надпочечников интактных крыс, но не у крыс, которым многократно вводили гидрокортизон для угнетения базальной активности гипоталамо-гипофизарно-надпочечниковой системы и у которых уровень рецепторов аминокислот был достоверно выше контроля. Предстрессовое введение баклофена и гамма-L-аминобутирилтаурина не изменяло специфическое связывание ГАМК, несмотря на влияние препаратов на концентрацию кортикостероидов в крови животных.

Ключевые слова: ГАМК, гипоталамо-гипофизарно-надпочечниковая система, гамма-L-аминобутирилтаурин, баклофен, энцефалопатия, аминокислоты – глутамат, спазм, нейротоксическое действие.

Baclofen (Baklosan, Lioresal) is a muscle relaxant, a derivative of GABA. Chemical the structure of its molecules is not similar to other muscle relaxants - unlike them, baclofen has no effect on mechanisms of neuromuscular transmission. Baclofen is a muscle relaxant, which is a beta-p-chlorophenyl derivative of one of inhibitory mediators - GABA. While using this drug, you may develop serious side effects. The development

of life-threatening conditions when using Baclofen may be the result of an unintentional overdose of a drug prescribed by a doctor, idiosyncrasy, suicidal behavior, or criminal acts. Purpose of the review: to consider the mechanisms of therapeutic and toxic action of Baclofen, its effects on cellular receptors to clarify the pathogenesis of life-threatening conditions caused by poisoning with this drug. Given the drug activates GABAB receptors due to which reduces the intensity of the release of excitatory amino acids - glutamate and aspartate, the action of which determines the occurrence of spasm.

Baclofen is available in oral and intrathecal forms (for intrathecal administration) and is widely used in clinical practice [2,3]. Indications for its applications are brain damage and spinal cord, including those of a traumatic nature, sclerosis with severe muscle spasticity, acute brain disorders blood circulation, meningitis.

Baclasan was shown to accumulate in brain tissue and have a direct neurotoxic effect. Encephalopathy may develop when baclofen is used. In particular, baclofen-associated encephalopathy was revealed in a study on rats that employed the dose of baclofen of 116 mg/kg. Encephalopathy with the triphasic acute waves, status epilepticus and isoelectric signals was diagnosed using EEG . In Ontario, a case record analysis of approximately 16,000 patients with kidney disease, who started taking baclofen between 2007 and 2018, was performed. Patients were divided into two groups receiving high and low doses of the drug. Patients from both groups were compared with almost 300,000 patients with kidney disease who had not received the drug. Among patients who received high doses of baclofen, 1.11% (108 out of 9707) were hospitalized with signs of cognitive impairment. This proportion was 0.42% (26 out of 6235) in the group of low-dose baclofen patients . A case of acute baclofen poisoning with a suicidal purpose resulting in deep coma has been reported. Interestingly, the «burst-suppression» EEG pattern was noted on the 1st day, which can be considered as one of the signs of a dying brain.

REFERENCES

1. Saodat, A., Vohid, A., Ravshan, N., & Shamshod, A. (2020). MRI study in patients with idiopathic coxarthrosis of the hip joint. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(2), 410-415.
2. Axmedov, S. J. (2023). EFFECTS OF THE DRUG MILDRONATE. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(20), 40-59.
3. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). ASCORBIC ACID: ITS ROLE IN IMMUNE SYSTEM, CHRONIC INFLAMMATION DISEASES AND ON THE ANTIOXIDANT EFFECTS. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 3(11), 57-60.

4. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). THE ROLE OF THIOTRIAZOLINE IN THE ORGANISM. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 9(5), 152-155.
5. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). HEPTRAL IS USED IN LIVER DISEASES. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 35(3), 76-78.
6. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). EFFECT OF TIVORTIN ON CARDIOMYOCYTE CELLS AND ITS ROLE IN MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 42, 255-257.
7. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). NEUROPROTECTIVE EFFECT OF CITICOLINE. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(1), 1-4.
8. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF TRIMETAZIDINE IN ISCHEMIC CARDIOMYOPATHY. *Journal of new century innovations*, 44(2), 3-8.
9. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). ВСЕ ЭФФЕКТЫ ПРЕПАРАТА ИМУДОН. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(2), 39-43.
10. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). SPECIFIC FEATURES OF THE EFFECT OF THE HEPARIN DRUG. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(2), 34-38.
11. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USE OF GLUCOCORTICOSTEROIDS IN PEDIATRIC PRACTICE. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(2), 29-33.
12. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). РОЛЬ ИНТЕЛЛАНОВОГО СИРОПА И ЦИАНОКОБАЛАМИНА В УЛУЧШЕНИИ ПАМЯТИ. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(2), 44-48.
13. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). TREATMENT OF POLYNEUROPATHY WITH BERLITHION. *Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi*, 4(1), 201-209.
14. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USE OF ASCORIL IN BRONCHIAL ASTHMA. *Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi*, 4(1), 191-200.
15. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DRUG ARTOXAN. *Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi*, 4(1), 182-190.
16. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF RENGALIN IN CHRONIC BRONCHITIS. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 116-123.
17. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF ALMAGEL DRUG IN GASTRIC AND DUODENAL WOUND DISEASE. *Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi*, 4(1), 173-181.

18. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF CODELAK BRONCHO SYRUP IN CHILDREN'S PRACTICE. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 109-115.
19. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE AEVIT DRUG EFFECT. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 124-132.
20. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF ALCHEBA DRUG IN POST-STROKE APHASIA. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 132-138.
21. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF HYALURON CHONDRO DRUG IN OSTEOARTHRISIS. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 139-145.
22. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). EFFECT OF SIMETHICONE DROP IN FLATULENCE. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(1), 95-101.
23. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). BENEFITS OF BETADINE SOLUTION. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(1), 116-122.
24. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). EFFECT INHALED GLUCOCORTICOIDS IN CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE AND BRONCHIAL ASTHMA. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(1), 171-180.
25. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USE OF VIGANTOL IN RICKETS. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(1), 102-108.
26. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE VITAPROST DRUG RESULTS. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(1), 109-115.
27. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF BISEPTOL DRUG IN URINARY TRACT DISEASE. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(1), 89-94.
28. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). PROPERTIES OF THE DRUG DORMIKIND. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(5), 88-92.
29. Jamshidovich, A. S., & Komilovich, E. B. (2024). IMMUNOMODULATORY FUNCTION OF DIBAZOL DRUG. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(5), 83-87.
30. Jamshidovich, A. S., & Komilovich, E. B. (2024). ADVANTAGES OF THE DRUG NEPTRAL. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(5), 98-101.

31. Эргашов, Б. К., & Ахмедов, Ш. Ж. (2024). ГИПЕРТОНИЧЕСКАЯ БОЛЕЗНЬ ЭТИОЛОГИЯ. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 59-69.
32. Komilovich, E. B., & Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). HYPERTENSION, CLASSIFICATION AND PATHOGENESIS. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 50-58.
33. Komilovich, E. B., & Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). YURAK ISHEMIYASI. STENOKARDIYADA SHOSHILINCH TIBBIY YORDAM. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 12-20.
34. Komilovich, E. B., & Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). HYPERTENSION ETIOLOGY. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 32-41.
35. Komilovich, E. B., & Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). CARDIAC ISCHEMIA. ANGINA NURSING DIAGNOSIS AND CARE. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 44-52.
36. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). IMPORTANT INDICATIONS OF THE DRUG WOBENZYM. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 29-32.
37. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE RESULTS OF THE EFFECT OF THE DRUG VALIDOL. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 19-23.
38. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). VIFERON USE IN CHILDREN. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 24-28.
39. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USE OF DUSPATALIN (MEBEVERINE HYDROCHLORIDE) IN GASTROINTESTINAL DISEASES. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(5), 93-97.
40. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). ЭФФЕКТЫ СИРОПА ДЕПАКИНА (ВАЛЬПРОЕВАЯ КИСЛОТА). *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 14(2), 148-152.
41. Jamshidovich, A. S., & Komilovich, E. B. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DRUG ALLOCHOL FOR CHRONIC CHOLECYSTITIS. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 14(2), 133-137.
42. Jamshidovich, A. S., & Komilovich, E. B. (2024). ВАЖНЫЕ СВОЙСТВА ПРЕПАРАТА ДЕ-НОЛ (субцитрат висмута). *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 14(2), 143-147.
43. Jamshidovich, A. S., & Komilovich, E. B. (2024). SPECIAL FEATURES OF BUDECTON DRUG. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 14(2), 138-142.
44. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). ЭФФЕКТИВНОЕ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЕ ПРЕПАРАТА КЕЙВЕР. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 15(3), 137-143.

45. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USEFUL PROPERTIES OF THE DRUG YODOFOL. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 15(3), 144-149.
46. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). FITOTERAPIYANING AKUSHER-GINEKOLOGIYADA ANAMIYATI. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 121-125.
47. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DRUG DOPROKIN. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 109-114.
48. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE EFFECT OF DOSTINEX ON THE BODY. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 115-120.
49. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО ДЕЙСТВИЯ ПРЕПАРАТА КАНЕФРОН. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 138-143.
50. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ЭФФЕКТЫ ПРЕПАРАТА ИНДОЛ. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 126-131.
51. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). EFFECT OF ISMIZHEN DRUG ON BODY IMMUNITY. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 132-137.
52. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). POSITIVE EFFECTS OF THE DRUG CARCIL. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 15(3), 127-131.
53. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО ДЕЙСТВИЯ КАВИНТОНА. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 15(3), 132-136.
54. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). Современный Эффект Спрея Мометазон. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 3(3), 62-65.
55. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF" SIMONTE PLUS" DRUG IN THE MODERN TREATMENT OF BRONCHIAL ASTHMA. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(5), 66-70.
56. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). FEATURES OF THE BIOMECHANISM OF THE DRUG LEVOMYCETIN (CHLORAMPHENICOL). *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(9), 298-301.
57. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE MOST IMPORTANT INDICATORS OF OMEGA 3 SUBSTANCE IN THE METABOLISM OF THE HUMAN BODY. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(10), 113-117.
58. Komilovich, E. B., & Khalimovich, M. N. (2024). CARDIAC ISCHEMIA. ANGINA CLINICAL FORMS AND DIAGNOSIS. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 70-78.

59. Komilovich, E. B. (2024). CORONARY HEART DISEASE. ANGINA EMERGENCY CARE. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(7), 235-242.
60. Komilovich, E. B. (2024). YURAK ISHEMIK KASALLIGI. STENOKARDIYANI DAVOLASHNING ZAMONAVIY TAMOYILLARI. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 3-11.
61. Komilovich, E. B., & Khalimovich, M. N. (2024). DEPENDENCIES IN THE CLINIC AND DIAGNOSIS OF CORONARY HEART DISEASE AND ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 61-69.
62. Komilovich, E. B., & Xalimovich, M. N. (2024). YURAK ISHEMIYASIDA HAMSHIRALIK DIAGNOSTIKASI VA PARVARISHI. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 79-85.
63. Komilovich, E. B., & Khalimovich, M. N. (2024). NURSING CARE FOR CORONARY ARTERY DISEASE, ANGINA PECTORIS. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 86-94.
64. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE MOST IMPORTANT BENEFITS OF GINGER FOR THE HUMAN BODY'S IMMUNITY. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(11), 269-273.
65. Xusenovich, M. S., & Turapjanovna, Z. M. (2024). SEMIZLIKNING TURLI FENOTIPLARDA KARDIOMETABOLIK XAVF OMILLARINI TAQQOSLASH. *SO 'NGI ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI*, 7(4), 112-116.
66. Husenovich, M. S., & Turabdjanovna, Z. M. (2024). STUDY OF DIURNAL PROFILE OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION IN DIFFERENT PHENOTYPE OBESITY. *образование наука и инновационные идеи в мире*, 43(1), 129-131.
67. Xusenovich, M. S. (2024, September). SEMIZLIKNI TURLI FENOTIPLARIDA YURAK QON-TOMIR KASALLIKLARINI KELIB CHIQISH XAVFI PROGNOZI. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 3, No. 26, pp. 15-18).
68. Xusenovich, M. S. (2024). O 'ZBEKISTONDA RESPUBLIKASIDA YURAK-QON TOMIR KASALLIKLARI TARQALISHI VA HOZIRGI KUNDAGI KO'RILAYOTGAN CHORA TADBIRLAR. *AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE*, 2(3), 79-82.
69. Xusenovich, M. S., & Allayarovich, A. A. (2024). O 'ZBEKISTONDA YURAK-QON TOMIR KASALLIKLARI TARQALISHI VA HOZIRGI KUNDAGI

TENDENSIYASI. *MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH*, 4(38), 54-57.

70. Ravshanovna, X. L. (2021, June). MINIMALLY INVASIVE METHODS OF TREATMENT OF DENTAL CARIES IN ADULTS. In " *ONLINE-CONFERENCES*" *PLATFORM* (pp. 118-119).